

1. Weight measure - global factor analysis

In addition to the characteristics of the objective, factor analysis (FA) can grasp the inherent information and potential relevance between indexes and reduce the information overlap between multiple indexes, therefore it is easier to extract the true characteristics of theme and reflects the influence in the degree of each index on the entire index system.

Using the FA method, the weight measurement includes two types: The first way determines the weight according to the coefficient of FA score function and the corresponding variance contribution rate. However, the weights are occasionally negative.

Therefore, we select the second way and determine the weight according to the communality of each index. The communality is the square sum of all common-factor loads, and the common factors reflect the common information of the index system after analyzing and summarizing the original index information.

With a higher communality value, other indexes can measure more common characteristics the index, the index is more likely to be explained by common factors, the explanatory power of the theme is stronger, and the index is more influential. Therefore, we can give a higher weight to the index that has greater communality values. Meanwhile, the GFA method is more holistic, uniform and comparable than the traditional FA method, and it can extract large sample information from the panel data. Therefore, we use GFA to determine the weight of the specific index as described below.

First, we establish the global data table: the $n \times m$ matrix $R_{n \times m}$ is established according to the m indexes of n regions and put $R_{n \times m}$ by year t to form a global data table K , where

$K = \{X^t \in R^{n \times m}, t = 1, 2, \dots, T\}$ X_t at a time t can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X^t_{11} & X^t_{12} & \cdots & X^t_{1m} \\ X^t_{21} & X^t_{22} & \cdots & X^t_{2m} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X^t_{n1} & X^t_{n2} & \cdots & X^t_{nm} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e^t_1 \\ e^t_2 \\ \vdots \\ e^t_n \end{bmatrix} \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T \quad (1)$$

Second, we standardize the global data table K : if x'_{ij} is a positive index:

$$x'_{ij} = (x_{ij} - x_{\min}) / (x_{\max} - x_{\min}) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, nT; j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (2)$$

Else,

$$x'_{ij} = (x_{\max} - x_{ij}) / (x_{\max} - x_{\min}) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, nT; j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (3)$$

Third, we calculate the global covariance matrix Σ , the eigenvalue $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_m$ of Σ , and the eigenvector $L = (l_1, l_2, \dots, l_m)$.

Fourth, according to the largest eigenvalues, we select the principal components $F_1, F_2, \dots, F_p$ as the common factor and make the cumulative variance contribution rate more than 85%. Then, we get the factor load matrix A :

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{\lambda_1}l_{11} & \cdots & \sqrt{\lambda_p}l_{1p} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sqrt{\lambda_1}l_{m1} & \cdots & \sqrt{\lambda_p}l_{mp} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The communality h_j^2 of each index is calculated as follows:

$$h_j^2 = \sum_{i=1}^p (\sqrt{\lambda_i}l_{ji})^2 = (\sqrt{\lambda_1}l_{j1})^2 + (\sqrt{\lambda_2}l_{j2})^2 + \cdots + (\sqrt{\lambda_p}l_{jp})^2 \quad (5)$$

Finally, we calculate the weight of each index:

$$\omega_j = \frac{h_j^2}{\sum_{j=1}^m h_j^2} \quad (6)$$

2. Index weighted scoring - weighted TOPSIS method

The main principle of the TOPSIS method is to evaluate the performance according to the distance between the evaluated object and the negative ideal point/benchmark. And we use the TOPSIS method to evaluate IGDP. The main steps are described below.

First, we calculate the weighting matrix, $R = (r_{ij})_{n \times m}$

$$r_{ij} = \omega_j \cdot x'_{ij} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, nT; j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (7)$$

where ω_j denotes the weight that is calculated in the above section.

Second, we determine the positive ideal point q_j^+ and the negative ideal point q_j^- :

$$q_j^+ = \max(r_{1j}, r_{2j}, \dots, r_{nj}), q_j^- = \min(r_{1j}, r_{2j}, \dots, r_{nj}) \quad (8)$$

Third, according to the ideal point q_j^+ and q_j^- , we calculate the Euclidean distance d_i^+ and d_i^- :

$$d_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m (q_j^+ - r_{ij})^2}, d_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m (r_{ij} - q_j^-)^2} \quad (9)$$

Finally, we calculate the performance P_i :

$$P_i = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^- + d_i^+} \quad (10)$$

The greater the P_i value, the better the performance of the evaluation object.